

Computer-Aided Load Estimation of Air-conditioning Systems for Non-residential and Residential Buildings

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Abstract

This study collected existing mathematical formulae that are essential for load estimation in residential and non-residential buildings, combined the formulae collected and wrote a computer algorithm that would effectively support load estimation in residential and non-residential buildings. The algorithm was used to develop interactive and user-friendly software for load estimation in residential and non-residential buildings. The software was developed using C# Programming Language and it is named Air-conditioner Load Estimator (ALE). The ALE has been evaluated and validated. Hence, using the air-conditioner loads for various buildings, both residential and non-residential cooling loads can be determined on the quickly without going through standard tables.

Keywords: Load estimation, Algorithm, Air-conditioner, Software, Validation.

Introduction

Air-conditioning is the process of altering the properties of air (primarily temperature and humidity) to achieve favourable conditions, typically with the aim of distributing the conditioned air to an occupied space to improve comfort (Jones, 1997). The air-conditioning system is a mechanical system which has been applied in supplying a controlled atmospheric condition to various housing units such as include; offices, living rooms, lecture theatres, industries and other dwelling units (Stoecker and Jones, 1982). Air-conditioners could be used to facilitate the comfort of humans and for the proper regulations and performance of some chemical

and physical processes in industries, (Shan, 2000). In the most general sense, air conditioning can refer to any form of technology, heating, cooling, dehumidification, humidification, cleaning, ventilation, or air movement that modifies the condition of air, (Jones, 2001). Technically, the air-conditioning process involves controlling some parameter of factors that describe the atmospheric conditions such as its purity, humidity of the air within some specifications indicated during the design of an air-conditioning system, (Jones, 1985). It is a mechanism designed to change the air temperature and humidity within an area as shown in Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Schematic of window type air conditioning system, (ASHRAE, 2001).

There is necessity of installing air-conditioners due to the intense heat generated in residential and non-residential buildings as a result of variation in climatic condition. Load estimation for the installation prior to installation of an air-conditioning system is very important in order to have optimal performance of the system in usage. Load estimating in air-conditioning system installation has been carried out manually in many developing countries especially in Nigeria. There are a lot of time wastage, stress, and some calculations errors that would be incurred in carrying out the load estimate manually for a more complex structure. Hence, the automation of the whole complicated process through the use of a Computer-Aided Design Software is expedient in reducing the errors that will be involved and in speeding-up the process. In order to achieve this fit, an Object-Oriented approach was used herein to develop the software. This involves the use of Microsoft Visual C#, with a more intuitive and interactive graphical user interface (GUI) through which the user key in all the parameters necessary for load estimation is done at the click of a button. The developed software is named Air-conditioner Load Estimator (ALE).

Cooling and heating load calculations should normally be made for heating, ventilating, and air-conditioning systems (HVAC) and their components (Ansari *et al*, 2005). In principle, the loads are calculated to maintain the indoor design conditions. The first step in load calculation is to establish the design criteria for the project which involves a consideration of the building concept, construction materials, occupancy patterns, density, available

Materials and Methods

Accurate load estimates are important prerequisites of a good air-conditioning system design. Ultimate system performance also depends on the proper system selections and is based on a reasonable load estimates. Building can be classified as envelope-load-dominated

equipment, lighting levels, comfort ranges, ventilations and space specific needs.

Cooling Load Estimation Techniques

To design an efficient and effective air conditioning system, the load must first be calculated using established techniques. The various methods in use are given as follows:

- (a) Total Equivalent Temperature Difference (TETD).
- (b) Cooling load Temperature Difference/ Cooling Load Factor. (CLTD/CLF).
- (c) Transfer Function Method (TFM).
- (d) Heat Balance (HB) and Radiant Time Series (RTS).
- (e) Manual J Method for Residential Applications and Manual method for Commercial Buildings:

These methods are simplified versions, jointly developed by Air-conditioning contractors of America (ACCA) and Air conditioning and Refrigeration Institute.

These different methods may yield different results for the same input data. This is primarily due to the way each method handles the solar effect and building dynamics. But in true sense all the above approaches attempts to consider the fundamental principle that heat flow rates are not instantaneously converted to loads and heat addition or extraction incident upon the building do not immediately result in a change in temperature. Thermally heavy buildings can effectively delay the cooling or heating load for several hours. Most designers use the TETD and CLTD methods because these methods give component loads and tend to predict load on the conservative side. For strictly manual cooling loads calculation method, the most practical to use is the CLTD/CLF method.

and interior-load-dominated. The envelope heat flows are termed “external loads”, in that they originate with the external environment. The other loads are termed “internal loads”, in that they are generated from within the building itself.

I. Non-Residential Buildings Cooling Load Estimation

Generally, the load components for estimating load capacity in air-conditioning system for a building are identified as follow:

External Loads: External loads consist of the following:-

- a. Sensible loads through opaque envelope assemblies (i.e. due to roofs, walls, floors)
- b. Sensible loads through transparent or translucent envelope assemblies (i.e. due to skylights, windows, glazed openings)
- c. Sensible loads through ventilation and infiltration (i.e. due to air leakage)
- d. Latent loads through ventilation and infiltration.

Sensible Heat Gain is the heat flowing into the building by conduction through exterior walls, floors, ceilings, doors and windows due to the temperature difference on their two sides; heat received from solar radiation directly through glass of windows, ventilators or doors and the heat absorbed by walls and roofs; the heat given off by lights; the heat liberated by the occupants and the heat carried by the outside air as result of infiltration and ventilation through the cracks in doors, windows, chairs, book-shelves etc and through their frequent openings.

Latent Heat Gain is the heat gain due to moisture in the outside air entering by infiltration and ventilation and the heat gain due to condensation of moisture from occupants.

In respect of the external load mentioned above the sensible load could be calculated in term of various components of non-residential building as follows:

- a. Roofs, External Walls & Conduction through Glass: The equation to calculate the cooling load due roofs, walls and the conductions through glass is as given in (1)

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = U \times A \times (\text{CLTD}) \quad (1)$$

where:

U is the thermal Transmittance for roof or wall or glass, A is the area of roof, wall or glass calculated from building plans, CLTD is the Cooling Load Temperature Difference for roof, walls, or glass, (ASHRAE, 2011).

The Thermal Transmittance used in this work is 0.62W/m²K for the Roof (U_r), 1.61 W/m²K

for the Wall (U_w) and 4.6W/m²K for 12mm thick Glass window (U_g), (ASHRAE, 2011).

Hence, the Summation of the sensible loads for the wall, roof and the glass window could be obtained.

- b. Partitions, Ceiling & Floors: The equation to calculate the cooling load due to partitions, ceiling and floors is as given in (2)

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = U \times A \times (T_a - T_c) \quad (2)$$

U = Thermal Transmittance for roof or wall or glass (ASHRAE, 2001).

A = area of partition, ceiling or floor calculated from building plans

T_a = Outside design temperature

T_c = Inside design temperature of conditioned space (assumed constant)

The U-values used in this research work according to ASHRAE, (2011) include:

1.47 W/m²K for partitions, 0.62 W/m²K for ceiling for floor

T_a and T_c are measured using a thermometer.

- c. Ventilation & Infiltration Air: Ventilation and Infiltration air is the amount of outdoor air required to maintain Indoor Air Quality for the occupants (ASHRAE, 2001) and makeup for air leaving the space due to equipment exhaust, ex-filtration and pressurization while Infiltration air is the amount of unconditioned air entering the conditioned space due to opening of some space. The equation to calculate the cooling load due to ventilation and infiltration air is as given in (3)

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = 8.6 \times \text{ACH} \times (\text{Volume of space}) \quad (3)$$

where:

ACH = Ventilation airflow rate/Volumetric air flow rate calculated as air change per hour

- d. Solar Load Through Glass: The equation to calculate the cooling load due to radiant sensible loads from the transparent/translucent elements such as window glass, skylights and plastic sheets is as given in (4)

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = A \times (\text{SHGC}) \times (\text{CLF}) \quad (4)$$

where:

A = area of roof, wall or glass calculated from building plans

SHGC = Solar Heat Gain Coefficient.

CLF = Solar Cooling Load Factor.

Q is in kW

In this research work, the Solar Heat Gain Capacity of the glass under consideration is taken as 0.65, (ASHRAE, 2011; Duffie and Backman, 1980; and Kreith and Kreider, 1978), while the Solar Cooling Load Factor is chosen based on the direction being faced by the glass.

Internal Loads: Internal cooling loads consist of the following:-

- a. Sensible and latent loads due to people
- b. Sensible loads due to lighting
- c. Sensible loads due to power loads and motors (elevators, pumps, fans & other machinery)
- d. Sensible & latent loads due to appliances

The equations used in estimating internal cooling loads in term of non-residential buildings components are:

- a. People: The equation to calculate the cooling load due to people is given as in (5) and (6):

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = N \times (Q_S) \times (CLF) = N \times SHG \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{\text{Latent}} = N \times (Q_L) = N \times LHG \quad (6)$$

N = number of people in space.

Q_S, Q_L = Sensible and Latent Head Load of Occupancy.

CLF = Cooling Load Factor, by hour of occupancy.

CLF = 1.0, if operation is 24 hours of cooling

Table 1 gives the value of the Sensible Heat Gain and the Latent Heat Gain for several activities of people.

Table 1: Sensible Heat Gain (SHG) and Latent Heat Gain (LHG) in respect of human activities

S/N	Activities	SHG (Watt)	LHG (Watt)
1	Seated at rest	60	40
2	Seated, very light work, writing	65	55
3	Seated, eating	75	95
4	Seated, light work, typing	75	75
5	Standing, light work, walking, slowly.	90	95
6	Light bench work	100	130
7	Light machine work	100	205
8	Heavy work	165	305
9	Moderate dancing	120	255
10	Athletics	185	340

Source: ASHRAE, 2011.

Since the space temperature is not maintained constant during the 24 hours period, then the Cooling Load Factor (CLF) is 1.

- b. Electric Lights: The equation to calculate the cooling load due to Electric lights is given as in (7):

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = 3.41 \times W \times FUT \times FBF \times (CLF) \quad (7)$$

W = Installed lamp watts input from electrical lighting plan or lighting load data

FUT = Lighting utilization factor

FBF = Blast factor allowance, as appropriate

CLF = Cooling Load Factor, by hour of occupancy. For this research, the Cooling Load Factor is 1.

The Wattage is determined by looking at the current rating of the lamp and multiplying that with the standard voltage (240 V). The Light Utilization factor (FUT) is calculated as the ratio of the light current in use to the total

number of light presently installed. The Blast factor allowance (FBF) is 1 for compact fluorescent Light (CFL) and 1.2 for ordinary fluorescent tube.

- c. Appliances: The equation to calculate the cooling load due to appliances is given as in (8):

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = 3.41 \times W \times F_u \times F_r \times (CLF) \quad (8)$$

W = Installed rating of appliances in watts according to the manufacturer's data.

F_u = Usage factor.

F_r = Radiation factor.

CLF = Cooling Load Factor, by hour of occupancy.

For the sake of this research work, the Cooling load factor for heavy equipment is taken as 0.16 while for light equipment is taken as 0.12, (ASHRAE, 2011).

Total Loads

The total load is the summation of external and internal load. Usually 10% safety margin is added. The final load is then used to size the HVAC equipment.

II. Residential Building Cooling Load Estimation

There are two main types of building that were considered when estimating air-conditional loads for residential buildings:

Single-family Unit (SFU): A house in this category usually has exposed walls in four directions, often more than one story, and a roof. The cooling system is single-zone, Unitary system with a single thermostat, Two-story houses may have a separate cooling system for each floor. The rooms are reasonably open and generally have a centralized air return. In this configuration, both air and load from rooms are mixed, and a load-leveling effect, which requires a distribution of air to each room that is different from a pure commercial system, results. Because the amount of air supplied to each room is based on the loads for that room, proper load calculation procedures must be used.

Multi-dwelling Unit (MDU): Unlike single-family detached units, multifamily units by definition do not have exposed surfaces facing in all directions. Rather, each unit has only one or two exposed surfaces and possibly a roof. Two exposed walls will be at right angles, and both east and west will not be exposed in a given living unit. Each living unit has a single unitary cooling system or a single fan-coil unit, and the rooms are relatively open to one another. This configuration does not have the same load-leveling effects as single-family units, but is not a commercial building.

In other to calculate the cooling loads for residential buildings, the following loads sources are considered:

(a) **Glass and Windows Area:** The equation to calculate the cooling load due to glass and windows is given as in (9):

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = (\text{GLF}) \times A \tag{9}$$

where:

GLF is the glass load factor and A is the summation of the areas in the different directions (N, NE, SE etc). Table 2 gives the glass loads factors assuming that the maximum temperature of 43 °C is attained in a day also with reference to the type of glass (single, double etc).

Table 2: Glass-Load Factor for Residential Buildings

Direction	Single Glass	Double Glass	Heat Absorbing Double Glass	Triple Glass
N	91	73	63	47
NE & NW	126	104	91	82
E & W	155	132	117	110
SE & SW	145	123	107	98
S	114	95	82	69

Source: ASHRAE, 2011.

(b) **Doors:** The equation to calculate the cooling load for doors is as follows:

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = U_d \times A \times (\text{CTLD}) \tag{10}$$

where:

U_d is the Transmittance/U-factor for door and A is the door area with respect to orientation. U_d is taken as 1.87 W/m²K (ASHRAE, 2011). The Cooling Load Temperature difference (CTLD) used is given as in Table 3.

(c) **External Walls:** The equation to calculate the cooling load due to external wall is as given in (11):

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = U_w \times A \times (\text{CTLD}) \tag{11}$$

where:

U_w is the U-factor for wall and given as 1.61 W/m²K (ASHRAE, 2011), A is the area in square meters while the CTLD is as given in Table 3.

(d) **Partitions to Unconditioned Space:** The equation to calculate the cooling load due to Partitions to Unconditioned Space in considering temperature difference across the partition is as given in (12):

$$Q = U_p \times A \times (T_a - T_c) \tag{12}$$

where:

U_p is the U-factor for partitions, A is area. U_p is taken as $1.47 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ (ASHRAE, 2011).

(e) Ceiling and Roofs: The equation to calculate the cooling load due to ceiling and roofs is as given in (13):

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = U_r \times A \times (\text{CLTD}) \quad (13)$$

where:

U_r is the U-factor, $0.62 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ (ASHRAE, 2011) for roofs and ceiling, A is the area in square meters while the CLTD is the cooling load temperature difference. CLTD value is as given in Table 3.

(f) Exposed Floors: The equation to calculate the cooling load due to exposed floors is as given in (14):

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = U_f \times A \times (\text{CLTD}) \quad (14)$$

Where:

U_f is the U-factor for floor, A is area and CLTD is as given in Table 3.

Infiltration: The equation to calculate the cooling load due to infiltration effect is as given in (15) and (16):

$$Q_{\text{Sensible}} = 1.2 \times Q \times (T_a - T_c) \quad (15)$$

$$Q = \frac{\text{ACH} \times (\text{room volume}) \times 1000}{3600} \quad (16)$$

where:

Q is the volumetric airflow rate (m^3/s), ACH is the air exchange rate. The value of ACH is taken as the average of the medium, tight and loose condition values considered in ASHRAE, 2011. ACH is taken as 0.573.

(g) Occupancy: The equation to calculate the cooling load due to occupant is as given in (17) and (18):

Sensible heat gain, $Q_s = \text{Sensible heat gain factor, } Q_{\text{SF}} \times \text{Number of occupants, } N \quad (17)$

Latent heat gain, $Q_L = \text{Latent heat gain factor, } Q_{\text{LF}} \times \text{Number of occupants, } N \quad (18)$

Generally, the cooling load due to one person in a room is taken as 67 W (ASHRAE, 2011), N is the number of occupant in a room.

Hence, the total load can be calculated as Latent Load Factor (1.17) \times Sum of the individual sensible load calculated.

Table 3: Cooling Load Temperature Difference for Different Sources for SFU Building and MDU

Walls and Doors (SFU)	Walls and Doors (MDU)	Roofs & Ceilings (Single family)	Roofs & Ceiling (Multi-family)	Exposed Floors
North-13	N-18	31	43	11
NE & NW-16	NE-20			
E & W-18	E-26			
SE & SW-17	SE-26			
S-14	S-24			
	SW-32			
	W-35			
	NW-28			

Source: ASHRAE, 2011.

Table 3 present the CLTD for different components of the different types of residential building, NE and NW represents North-East and North-West respectively, E and W represents East and the West respectively, SE and SW represents South-East and South-West respectively and S represents South.

Software Implementation

The formulae needed for determining the cooling load for non-residential and residential building compile discussed in

sections I and II were implemented through software developed herein. The software called air-conditioner load estimator was developed using visual C# 2012 integrated development emolument (IDE)

When the software is triggered a welcome audio sound and a graphical user interface (GUI) showing several buttons textboxes and pictures explaining the functions of each window in the tab panel is launched. Fig. 2 shows the main features of the login and home page of the software.

Fig. 2: Air-conditioner Load Estimator Software Login Page.

Basically, the software is divided into two major interfaces windows according to its functionality: These are the non-residential and the residential building cooling load estimation input interfaces. Both interfaces contain details of the input to be supplied by the user to facilitate determination of the respective

cooling loads. There are five input interfaces for non-residential building cooling load estimation namely: Roof, External Walls and Glass Panel GUI, Building occupancy GUI, Ventilation, Partition, Ceiling and Floor GUI, Light and Equipment GUI and Solar GUI.

Fig. 3: Building Occupancy GUI for non-residential building CLC.

Fig. 4: Ventilation, Partition, Ceiling and Floor GUI for non-residential building CLC.

Also, for residential building cooling load estimation, there are eight input interfaces namely: Glass and Windows GUI, Doors GUI,

Externals Walls GUI, Partitions of Unconditioned Space GUI, Ceiling and Roofs GUI, Exposed Roof GUI, Infiltrations GUI and Building Occupancy GUI.

Fig. 5: Building Occupancy GUI for residential building CLC.

Fig. 6: Ceiling and Roofs GUI for residential building CLC.

As an example, see Figures 3 and 4 for the building occupancy GUI and Ventilation, Partition, Ceiling and Floor GUI for non-residential building cooling load calculation (CLC) respectively.

Also, Figures 5 and 6 show the building occupancy GUI and Ceiling and Roofs GUI for residential building CLC respectively.

Generally, the air-conditioner cooling load estimator prompted the user for a password. Immediately, the user launched it and if the user enters the correct password the home page of the software opens. Thereafter, the relevant

input information relating to the loads starting from the roof, external wall and conduction through glass are entered by the user and the computation is done after the user must have clicked the compute key, i.e. the corresponding load is computed.

If there are other information relating to the load due to occupancy, ventilation, partition and ceiling floors etc and the user enters this information, then the total load due to these sources are computed and displayed in the grid layout (see Fig. 7). Some values will be provided by the user and entered into the

appropriate fields and the total load will be computed and compared with the results of

calculating the loads manually.

Fig. 7: Computed loads.

Results and Discussions

Three set of data were obtained and utilized to test run the developed software. These data could be categorized into three cases. Data for case 1 provided on Table 4 and 5 was obtained from a residential building. The data on Table 6 were obtained from a non-residential building and is used as case 2. Another set of data given on Table 7 was also obtained from school of Engineering and Engineering Technology, FUTA conference room. This is case 3 which can also be categorized under non-residential building. The three sets of data were used to estimate cooling load for the building using the air-conditioner

load estimator software. Also, manual calculations were used to estimate the cooling loads for the buildings in respect of the data. Results show that the cooling load estimates obtained from the software are in agreement with those obtained from manual calculation using the assembled formulae (see Table 8, 9 and 10). Also, it was observed that while it took the software about 95 seconds (1.583 minutes) to execute the load estimation for a building, on the average, it took approximately 80 minutes to do the same for manual calculation. This implies that the software possesses a productivity which is approximately 50.5 times in comparison to manual calculation

Table 4: Data set 1 for case 1- Residential Building

Direction	Glass and Windows (m ²)	Doors (m ²)	External Walls (m ²)	Partitions of Unconditioned Space (m ²)	Ceiling & Roofs (m ²)	Exposed Floors (m ²)
North- Facing	12	3.5	12	13	12	12
West-Facing	12	4	12	6.5	12	12
South-Facing	12	4	12	6	12	12
East-Facing	12	3	12	7.5	12	12

Table 5: Data set 2 for case 1- Residential Building

Infiltration Loads	Occupancy/Internal Loads	Building Type	Temperature (°C)
Room Width = 12m	Population = 3	Single family	Internal Temperature = 25
Room Height = 4m Room Length = 12m			External Temperature = 27-35

Table 6: Data set for case 2- Non-Residential Buildings

Cooling Load Source	Information (Area, direction...) for 1600 hr of measurement.
Roof	Area = $12m^2$
Glass	Area = $12m^2$
External Wall(North)	Area = $5m^2$
External Wall(South)	Area = $5m^2$
Occupancy	Person Seated at rest = 2 Persons standing and walking slowly = 2
Partitions	Area = $3m^2$
Ceiling	Area = $12m^2$
Expose Floor	Area = $12m^2$
Light and Equipment	Apartment = Heavy e.g. Conference, CFL: Total = 8, in use = 4, Total Wattage = 9600W. Total Number of Equipment = 4, heavy = 2 (washing machine and fridge), medium = 2 (bread toaster and grinder).
Solar(North)	Area = $12m^2$, Glass State = Closed
Solar(South)	Area = $12m^2$, Glass State = Closed

Table 7: Data set for case 3- School of Engineering Building Conference Room.

CONFERENCE ROOM INFORMATION OF THE SEET BUILDING	
Cooling Load Source	Information (Area, direction) for 1300 hr of measurement.
Roof	Area = $8 * 5 = 40m^2$
Glass(Window)	Area = $0.8 * 1.2 = 0.96m^2$ per glass For 8 glasses we have: $0.96 * 8 = 7.68m^2$
External Wall(North)	Area = $(8*4)-(7.68) = 32.32m^2$, i.e. the area of the side of the external wall facing the northern direction – area of the window glass.
External Wall(East)	Area = $5 * 4 = 20m^2$
Occupancy	The number of chairs in the conference room is 40 and hence, the number of persons estimated to be seated in the room is given as 40, and it is most likely that there would be one person making a formal presentation hence, the total number of persons available is summed up to 41, and an excess of 43 for the sake of an expected error margin. Summarily, 42 persons will be seated and probably talking and writing, while 1 person will be standing, walking and talking.
Partitions	There are no partitions
Ceiling	Area = $40m^2$
Expose Floor	Area = $40m^2$
Light and Equipment	Apartment type =Conference room which corresponds to medium type, CFL: Total = 9, in use = 9, Total Wattage = $30W * 9 = 270W$. Total Number of Equipment = 5, heavy = 1(projector/165W); medium = 4 (fans/100W per one); Wattage for projector = 165Watts ;Wattage for all Fans = 400Watts
Solar(North) for glass	Area = $7.68m^2$, Glass State = Closed

Table 8: Result of Load Estimation for case 1

Load sources	Glass and Windows Load (Watts)	Door Loads (Watts)	External Wall Loads (Watts)	Partition Loads (Watts)	Ceiling/Roof Loads (Watts)	Exposed Floor Loads (Watts)	Infiltration Loads (Watts)	Occupancy Load(Watts)	Total Loads (Watts)
ALE Estimated Load (Watts)	6180	425.425	1262.52	145.53	922.56	327.36	3300.048	201	11258.54
Manuals Estimate Load (Watts)	6180	425.425	1262.52	145.53	922.56	327.36	3300.048	201	11258.54

Table 9: Result of Load Estimation for case 2

Load Sources	Roof, External Wall and Conduction through Glass	Occupancy	Ventilation, Partition, Ceiling and Floor	Light and Other Equipment	Solar	Total Estimated Load
ALE Estimated Load (Watts)	851.17	570	129.078	16368	1171.8	19538.718
Manuals Estimate Load (Watts)	851.17	570	129.078	16368	1171.8	19538.718

Table 10: Result of Load Estimation for case 3

Load Sources	Roof, External Wall and Conduction through Glass	Occupancy	Ventilation, Partition, Ceiling and Floor	Light and Other Equipment	Solar	Total Estimated Load
ALE Estimated Load (Watts)	1768.9184	5225	386.16	767.34548	345.6	8493.02388
Manuals Estimate Load (Watts)	1768.9184	5225	386.16	767.34548	345.6	8493.02388

The value of the total load obtained in case 1 is 11258.54 Watts, case 2 is 19538.718 Watts and also in case 3 is 8493.02388 Watts. The actual

capacity of the air-conditioning system for case 1 is 15 hp, case 2 is 25 hp and case 3 is 10 hp.

Conclusion

This study had compiled and assembled equations necessary for the determination of cooling load estimated of residential and non-residential building. The equations have been used to develop software called ALE for cooling load estimation of the building. The

software implementation of the air-conditioner load estimator, ALE has been validated and hence, the air-conditioner loads for various buildings (both residential and non-residential) can be determined. Important values and information can be keyed into the software and on the click of a button, cooling loads can be estimated.

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